

FOLK LANGUAGE MEANS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. This article highlights the issues of the role of folk language tools in the development of speech competence of younger schoolchildren in the process of learning Russian (native) language, general concepts are given to such types of folk language tools as riddles, proverbs, and sayings. According to the author, linguistic and speech competencies develop and are formed only with the correct and purposeful activity of the teacher. The article also highlights the main ways that contribute to the formation of speech and linguistic competence of primary school students.

Keywords: literary reading, creativity, ability, development of creative abilities, methods, literary reading lesson, relevance, techniques, activation.

НАРОДНЫЕ ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ СРЕДСТВА В РАЗВИТИИ РЕЧИ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье освещаются вопросы роли народных языковых средств в развитии речевой компетентности младших школьников в процессе изучения русского (родного) языка, даются общие понятия о таких видах народных языковых средств, как загадки, пословицы, поговорки. По мнению автора, языковая и речевая компетенции развиваются и формируются только при правильной и целенаправленной деятельности учителя. Также в статье выделены основные способы, способствующие формированию речевой и языковой компетентности учащихся начальных классов.

Ключевые слова: литературное чтение, творчество, способности, развитие творческих способностей, методы, урок литературного чтения, актуальность, приемы, активизация.

In accordance with the new curriculum Functionally oriented training provides, on the one hand, a basic model, and on the other, variable components that are reflected in goals, content, and methods.

The implementation of these goals is achieved in the process of formation and development of the following subject competencies of students:

This is "Speech and linguistic (linguistic) competences. What should be understood by these competencies?

Under language competence should be understood - this students' proficiency in all types of speech activities (reading, writing, listening, speaking) and the basics of the culture of oral and written speech, basic abilities and skills in using language in various areas and communication situations.

Linguistic (linguistic) competence should be understood- This knowledge of the basics of science about the Russian language by schoolchildren, its structure, development, functioning; also mastering a system of linguistic concepts from the field of phonetics, vocabulary, word formation, morphology and syntax; the student's ability to use words, their forms, syntactic structures in accordance with the norms of the Russian literary language, to use its synonymous means, ultimately - mastery of the richness of the native language as a condition for successful speech activity; the ability to enrich your vocabulary, analyze and evaluate linguistic phenomena and facts, and be able to use various linguistic dictionaries.

The widespread use of language means created by the people in the educational process is one of the effective ways to educate speech culture and develop the speech of the younger generation. Folk language means include riddles, proverbs and sayings.

The development of thinking, both logical and figurative, as well as the development of students' speech, is most facilitated by the construction of metaphorical riddles: children practically learn the mechanism of transfer - their speech is enriched by the motivated use of words in a figurative meaning.

It should be said that riddles are varied in their artistic structure. A riddle can be a directly posed question (often playful, of a humorous nature), or a description of the actions of an unnamed object, or a figurative definition of certain of its characteristics, or a detailed comparison (including a negative one), or a metaphor.

Riddles are one of the folk language means, types of didactic material and folklore genre. Riddles can be used in grades 1–4 when teaching literacy, writing, reading, and also in all grades as language material for analysis and exercises. They are distinguished by the clarity of phrase construction, conciseness, and imagery. For example: If it falls - it jumps, it gets hit - it doesn't cry (the ball). Flows, flows - it won't run out, runs, runs - won't run out (river). Seventy clothes,

and all without fasteners (a head of cabbage). I won't let a stranger into my house, I'm sad without the owner. and etc.

The teacher can use riddle materials for exercises to develop students' speech and linguistic competence. For example, when studying grammar, from the 2nd to the 4th grades and older (themes "Noun", "Adjective", "Verb", "Numerals", "Adverbs", etc. The tasks can be very diverse:

1. Read and guess the riddles. Write down the nouns in them.

- Who sleeps in a den in winter? (bear)
- How does a person see ahead? (mind).
- Cups are white on the bushes: in them

And threads and shirts (cotton).

2. Remember the riddles whose texts contain numerals.

Sample: Five brothers are equal in years, different in height (fingers). Two heads, two arms, six legs and one tail, and walks on four (a horseman). Five closets, one door (gloves). Seven brothers have one sister. Are there many of them? (eight).

3. Write down 3–4 riddles that use verbs.

Sample: It flies - howls, sits - digs the ground (beetle). I don't fly, I don't walk, but I'll come back and buzz; when I get tired, I'll stop, fall and lie down (a top).

Riddles-questions like: Increase interest in various linguistic phenomena:

A and B were sitting on the pipe,

A - fell, B - disappeared,

What's left on the pipe? (AND).

A.N. Tolstoy wrote about this: "It is in vain to think that oral literature was only the fruit of popular leisure. She was the dignity and intelligence of the people. She formed and strengthened his moral character, was his historical memory."

The use of Russian and (other) folk proverbs and sayings plays an important role in enriching the vocabulary and speech competence of students and in nurturing a culture of speech.

What are proverbs and sayings? What are their advantages?

A proverb is a short, frequently used, rhythmically constructed saying that contains an allegory, an image that concentrates life experience, and therefore is applicable to life situations; one of the types of oral folk art: To live is to serve the Motherland, If you make people laugh, you make people laugh, etc. Proverbs can be widely used in the learning process - both for educational purposes and for the development of speech competence, for the analysis of syntactic structures, images, etc. Thus, the textbook "Russian Language and Reading Literacy" for grade 2 presents

about 60 proverbs and more than 30 riddles. Many topics in the textbook begin with proverbs (A close-knit family knows no sadness. A tree is held together by its roots, and a person is a family.

The whole family is together, so is the soul in place. Harmony in the family is wealth. With the sun it is warm, with a mother – goodness. Alone in the field is not warrior. Without labor, rest is not sweet), etc.

Each proverb is an example of laconicism, clarity of construction, an example of the use of antithesis, tropes, ellipses, hyperboles, allegories, and personifications. In speech, students themselves very rarely use proverbs and have a decreasing tendency towards higher grades, which is apparently due to the loss of elements of colloquial and folk poetic styles, with the development of a scientific style, and with the influence of written and book styles.

The teacher often turns to proverbs and sayings when studying many topics, especially antonyms, synonyms (grades 2 - 4) with the following tasks:

1. Read the proverbs and write down antonyms from them.

Labor feeds, but laziness spoils. If you sow thickly, it will not be empty. A small deed is better than a big idleness. Good will not die, but evil will disappear. Listen more, talk less. Truth is not friendly with lies.

2. Remember and write down 3–4 proverbs and sayings about work and friendship in your notebook.

Sample: Nothing comes without effort. Without labor there is no fruit. Working hands never experience boredom. The field loves work. A tree is valued by its fruits, and a person by its deeds. The sun paints the earth, and labor paints man. Where there is peace and harmony, there is treasure.

Where there is peace, there is joy. I read the book and met a friend.

3. Find the matches of proverbs and sayings from the left column. Determine their overall theme.

The truth does not drown in water...	(that true hero).
For a just cause...	(you yourself will disappear).
Who stands up for the truth...	(to make people laugh).
You will destroy the truth and...	(stand boldly).
Living a lie...	(and does not burn in fire).

4. Write down 4 – 5 proverbs and sayings, consisting only of nouns. Explain the meaning of the written aphorisms.

Sample: The face is the mirror of the soul. Cleanliness is the key to health. Learning is light, ignorance is darkness.

5. Write down proverbs and sayings, underline the pronouns in them, determine their category.

All for one, one for all. Every young man has his own trick. He who dared mounted a horse. He who loves whom loves him. Tell me who you are friends with, and I will tell you who you are.

6. From different sources, write down 4 - 5 proverbs and sayings with numerals.

Sample: One wise head feeds a hundred heads. Don't have a hundred rubles - have a hundred friends.

Many such exercises are presented in school textbooks on the Russian language, in teaching aids, and in "Didactic Material" collections.

Proverbs and sayings, as well as other types of oral folk art, contain folk wisdom. Giving an assessment of a person, his business and moral qualities, culture, including linguistic, they mercilessly criticize all kinds of shortcomings:

Know a bird by its feathers, and a young man by his speech.

Learning is beauty, not learning is blindness.

The educational and didactic possibilities of these folklore genres are truly diverse. Riddles, proverbs and sayings form a love for folk art, for living figurative words, introduce children into the world of folk poetry, giving them aesthetic pleasure.

Thus, riddles, proverbs and sayings, fairy tales decorate our speech, giving it a special flavor, capacity, melodiousness, and teach kindness, love for the native word, the land of origin and everything without which there is no person.

The mysteries created by the Russian and Uzbek people cover literally all aspects of their social existence. Most of them are connected with the working way of life of peasants, with agriculture, gardening and housework; the riddles included the concepts of the flora and home world in their circle of interests, many household items were included in them, and folk customs and morals were also conveyed.

Using riddles, proverbs and sayings (Russian and Uzbek) as additional material in Russian lessons, the teacher must first think about in what class, at what stage of the lesson, how and for what purpose he will use them. Folklore genre materials must correspond to the topic of the lesson, the level of preparedness of the class and should be aimed and aimed at both activating cognitive activity and developing the speech and linguistic competence of primary, middle and high school students.

The effectiveness of the educational process is ultimately determined by the nature of the students' activities. If the teacher has not been able to organize a kind of creative and active activity of students, especially younger schoolchildren, meaningful and reasonable communication between them, he will not achieve much success.

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